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ABSTRACT

Moringa oleifera, often known as the "horseradish tree" or "Miracle Tree" or "drumstick tree," is a beneficial tree native to India that provides a plethora of advantages. According to several sources, the *Moringa* tree has lately gained popularity in Ethiopia owing to its many applications. *Moringa oleifera* is known as the "Miracle Tree" since all of its components are useful for nutritional and medicinal purposes. The *Moringa* tree can also help with soil and water conservation and climate change mitigation. Minerals, vitamins, and other important compounds abound in the leaves. The leaves' extracts are used to treat malnutrition and to supplement breast milk in nursing mothers. It has antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and antibacterial properties. A natural coagulant, *Moringa oleifera* seed, is widely utilized in water treatment.

Key Words: *Moringa oleifera*, Nutrition, Medicine, Tree, *Moringa* leaves

OBJECTIVES

- ❑ To study the beneficial effects of *Moringa oleifera* in a netshell
- ❑ To go through the therapeutic and nutritional characteristics of this plant.

INTRODUCTION

- *Moringa oleifera* (MO) is a plant native to India that thrives in tropical and subtropical climates across the world. It's also known as a 'drumstick tree' or a 'horseradish tree.'
- Minerals, vitamins, and other essential phytochemicals abound in the leaves. The leaves' extracts are used to treat malnutrition and to supplement breast milk in nursing mothers. It has antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and antibacterial properties.
- *Moringa oleifera* is a natural coagulant, *oleifera* seed, is widely utilized in water treatment. Minerals and critical amino acids are also abundant in *Moringa oleifera*. *Moringa* can be used in pig and rabbit reproduction as well.
- *Moringa* is regarded as one of the world's most beneficial trees. Its importance as animal feed is supported by its higher nutritional quality and high biomass output, especially during the dry season.
- The use of *Moringa* across disciplines for its medicinal value and deals with cultivation, nutrition, commercial and prominent pharmacological properties of this "Miracle Tree".

MATERIAL & METHODS

- Fresh leaves were procured, thoroughly cleaned to manually remove stem, dirt and other extraneous matter to produce high quality dehydrated powder.
- The leaf samples were shade dried till they turned crisp with the moisture level reduced up-to 10%. The dried leaves were ground to a homogenous mixture for particle reduction of 100 and stored in air tight container till further processing. analysed using kjeldhal method (N x 6.25).
- The iron, potassium, phosphorous and calcium levels were analysed by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer for antioxidant scavenging activity and storage stability.

REFERENCES

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RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- ❑ Minerals such as calcium, potassium, zinc, magnesium iron and copper are abundant in the leaves of *Moringa oleifera*. Because the leaves are low in calories, they can be included in an obese person's diet. The leaves are very high in protein and minerals (Daba, 2016), and contain all necessary amino acids. Pods are abundant in fiber and protein, and are used to treat digestive issues and colon cancer (Gandhi, 2018).
- ❑ Vitamin A, vitamin B, beta-carotene, pyridoxine, nicotinic acid, vitamin C, vitamin D, and vitamin E are all rich in *Moringa oleifera*.
- ❑ *Moringa oleifera* also includes anti-cancer substances including glucosinolates, isothio cyanates, glycoside compounds, and glycerol-1-9-octadecanoate, as well as important phytochemicals like tannin, sterols, terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, anthraquinones, alkaloids, and reducing sugar. In *Moringa* leaves, oligosaccharides and oxalate have been identified as anti-nutrient factors (Anthanont *et al.*, 2016).
- ❑ After 4 and 3 months of storage, dried leaves (*Moringa oleifera*) contained 87.5 percent and 50% of carotene, respectively, and could therefore be processed for practical use (Anwar *et al.*, 2005; Anwar *et al.*, 2007).

- ❑ The phytochemicals produced from MO seed extracts are efficient mosquito vector control agents, and the plant extracts might be utilized in future IPM programmes (Ali *et al.*, 2014; Al-Malki and Rabey, 2015; Ali *et al.*, 2019).
- ❑ In addition, it contains various other nutrients, including the following essential amino acids (Wasif *et al.*, 2014).
- ❑ *Moringa* species have a high phenolic content, which contributes to their strong antioxidant activity.
- ❑ Antioxidants, particularly polyphenols, are the major plant chemicals capable of reducing oxidative damage in tissues by indirect cell promotion or free radical scavenging (Ali *et al.*, 2014; Al-Malki and Rabey, 2015).

CONCLUSION

Moringa is a miracle tree that is locally available to the common man both in India and other countries, because of the nutritional and medicinal importance of moringa, the demand for moringa and its value added products are increasing which in turn demands for year round supply further research needs to be focused to develop the moringa industry tailoring it to improve livelihood, nutrition and poverty.